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Mathematical Task Modification for Higher Cognitive Demand and Mathematics Achievement of Students

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Abstract

Mathematics education plays a vital role in developing students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. However, many instructional materials and practices tend to focus on tasks that require only lower-level cognitive demands, potentially limiting students' growth in higher-order thinking skills. This study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of modified mathematical tasks designed for higher cognitive demand on the mathematics achievement of Grade 10 students. Both descriptive and quasi-experimental designs were employed to describe the mathematical tasks in the Simplified Self-Learning Module (SSLM) and compare the achievements of the students in the experimental and control groups. The experimental group was introduced to higher cognitive demand tasks, while the control group was taught using the SSLM. Results of the study revealed that, based on the number of items, most of the tasks in the SSLM for Mathematics Grade 10 are at lower cognitive demand levels, particularly procedures without connections. Many students using the SSLM remained stagnant in performance, suggesting that current instruction utilizing the SSLM is insufficient in significantly boosting cognitive performance. Conversely, mathematical task modification was highly effective in enhancing achievement and improving students' performance on tasks that require higher-level cognition. This study highlights that well-designed tasks are crucial for developing higher-order thinking skills and improving educational outcomes.

Keywords: *cognitive demand, mathematical task, mathematics achievement, task modification, higher-order thinking*

Introduction

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) reported in 2019 that the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) revealed a significant disparity in achievement levels among students from different countries, with the Philippines ranking notably low in Mathematics. In the 2022 PISA, the Philippines improved its ranking to 6th from the last in mathematics performance, but the students' average score of 355 points was still far below the international average of 472 (Bautista, 2023). Notably, mathematics low performers showed improvement in the 2022 PISA, with 84% scoring below Level 2 (OECD, 2022). Most Filipino students could only perform tasks at low cognitive demand levels, representing simple mathematical situations. Almost none of the Filipino students were among the top performers who attained Level 5 or 6 on the PISA test.

In the Philippine classroom setting, mathematics tasks are normally presented in a way that learners memorize concepts. These low cognitive demand tasks primarily involve recalling facts and procedures and applying them in familiar contexts. When teachers introduce learners to lower cognitive demand tasks, students do not have the opportunity to develop a deep understanding of concepts, leading to lower achievement in mathematical thinking and reasoning (Antonijević, 2016). Tasks requiring low cognitive demand can cause students to become disengaged or bored, leading to decreased attention spans and motivation to participate in learning activities (Tekkumru-Kisa et al., 2015).

Conversely, when students are exposed to tasks with higher cognitive demands, they develop better reasoning and critical thinking skills. While it is essential to include tasks of varying complexity based on specific learning objectives, students should ideally encounter tasks that require significant cognitive effort. Research synthesis indicates that curricula featuring tasks with high cognitive demands enhance students' conceptual understanding of crucial mathematical concepts. These tasks also improve students' reasoning, communication, problem-solving skills, and their ability to make mathematical connections, positively impacting their performance on both state and national achievement assessments (Boston & Wolf, 2006). High-performing countries value higher cognitive demand for learners to achieve better in mathematics. Therefore, it is vital to integrate high cognitive demand tasks and to identify and select high-quality tasks. Effective mathematical tasks provide entry points for every student in the class while also offering opportunities for exploration, ensuring that all students remain engaged in mathematical thinking (North Carolina Collaborative for Mathematics Learning, 2018).

The cognitive demand level of a task reflects the complexity and cognitive processes it requires from students. Stein et al. (2000) proposed cognitive demand levels such as memorization, procedural tasks without connections, procedural tasks with connections, and authentic problem-solving, with the latter representing the highest cognitive demands. Engaging students in tasks with high cognitive demands fosters skills such as sense-making, reasoning, critique, and justification. Thoughtful planning in task implementation is essential for facilitating student learning, with teachers having the flexibility to adjust the cognitive level according to student needs. According to Parrish et al. (2022), mathematical tasks provided to students should be based on their cognitive demands which refer to the level of thinking and reasoning required to solve them. Appropriately matching tasks to students' current levels of understanding and skill allows teachers to provide learning experiences that are neither too easy nor too challenging, promoting optimal learning

outcomes.

Teachers must expand their understanding of how to support students in learning challenging tasks effectively. Research suggests that optimal learning outcomes are achieved when tasks are structured to actively engage students in advanced cognitive processes. Selecting activities that promote higher-order thinking skills is significant in educational practices (Lester & Cai, 2016).

Given the significance of cognitive demand in task performance and the need for learners to improve in Mathematics, this research aims to determine the cognitive demand levels of the mathematical tasks encountered by Grade 10 students in the learning module. Investigating the cognitive demand of tasks, problems, or activities can offer valuable insights into the cognitive processes, skills, and strategies experienced by students. This study also intends to enhance the cognitive demands of the mathematical tasks in the module and measure the impact on students' learning outcomes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the cognitive demand of mathematical tasks provided to Grade 10 students. It also endeavored to enhance the cognitive demands in mathematical tasks and measure to what extent it improved students' learning. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the cognitive demand level of the mathematical tasks in the Simplified Self-Learning Module (SSLM) for Mathematics in Grade 10?
2. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test scores between the experimental and control groups?
3. Is there a significant difference in the post-test scores between the experimental and control groups?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the control and experimental groups?
5. Is there a significant difference in the gain scores between the experimental and control groups?

Methodology

Research Design

This research used a descriptive and quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test control group design. Descriptive research characterized the cognitive demand level of mathematical tasks in the Grade 10 Simplified Self-Learning Module (SSLM), covering lessons on permutations, combinations, and probability of simple events. Two student groups were compared based on their pre-tests, post-tests, and mean gain scores: the control group was exposed to mathematical tasks in the module, while the experimental group was exposed to modified tasks with higher cognitive demands.

Respondents

The Grade 10 students in two sections of the Amas National High School served as respondents to the study. There were 32 students in the experimental group who were exposed to tasks of higher cognitive demands. On the other hand, the control group had 30 students who were exposed to cognitive tasks demanded by the various activities intended for practice in the SSLM.

Two comparable intact groups were chosen from the Grade 10 sections of Amas National High School. The two sections were assigned as experimental and control groups by drawing lots.

Instrument

This study used the SSLM for Mathematics Grade 10. The self-learning module, authored by the Division of Kidapawan City SSLM writers, covers lessons on permutations, combinations, and probability of simple events. These activities were used for the control group and served as the basis for the modified tasks given to the experimental group.

The Task Analysis Guide (TAG) by Stein et al. (2000) was used to analyze the cognitive demand levels of the mathematical tasks in the SSLM, covering permutations, combinations, and probability of simple events. A mathematics achievement test, with a total of 20 points, served as both the pre-test and post-test for the control and experimental groups. The test equally distributed points across four cognitive demand levels. Level 1 (memorization) had 5 multiple-choice items, 1 point each, Levels 2 (procedure without connection) and 3 (procedure with connection) had 4 multiple-choice items and 1 open-ended problem, 1 point each, and Level 4 (doing mathematics) had 1 open-ended situation where students created problems, devised solutions, and made conclusions or decisions, worth 5 points and graded with a scoring rubric. The test items were adapted and revised from the SSLM, and content validity was ensured by three mathematics experts.

Procedure

Before data gathering, the researcher sent a letter to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent, asking for permission to conduct a study. When the approval was given, another letter was sent to the school principal to allow the researcher to conduct the study.

To gather the needed data for this study, the researcher implemented the following activities:

Analysis of Mathematical Tasks. In analyzing the mathematical tasks, the activities for the topics in permutations and combinations,

and the probability of simple events were gathered. There was a total of 69 items in the 8 activities from the self-learning modules which were subjected to analysis. These were analyzed with the use of the Task Analysis Guide (TAG) by Stein et al. (2000). To confirm that the items analyzed belong to such cognitive demand level, the analysis results were validated and confirmed by three Mathematics experts.

Modifying Mathematical Tasks into Higher Cognitive Demands. To enhance or modify the mathematical tasks into higher cognitive demands, the following strategies were used (Leinwand et al., 2014): prompting students to create real-world scenarios, introducing tasks "out of sequence," removing restrictive elements, encouraging repeated reasoning and pattern finding, prompting written reflections on mathematical concepts, fostering pattern identification and conjecture making, requiring generalizations, and promoting comparison of solution paths while articulating relationships between strategies or concepts. These approaches challenge students to think critically, creatively, and analytically, ultimately enhancing their mathematical proficiency. To ensure that the modified tasks are in higher cognitive demand, three Mathematics experts were requested to check and validate the tasks with the use of TAG. This was done before the tasks were introduced to the learners.

For each activity found in the SSLM, a corresponding activity with higher cognitive demand was created. Presented in Figure 2 is an example of a task from SSLM and below it is the corresponding task modification from level 2 (procedure without connection) to level 4 (doing mathematics) where learners create a problem and show solutions to the problem. In addition, all work examples in the module were also modified to higher cognitive demand tasks. The modified tasks tackled during the class discussion were meant to guide students in answering higher cognitive tasks. This helped them prepare and get ready to tackle more tasks with higher cognitive demands.

EXAMPLES

1.) Find the distinguishable permutations of the letters of each word.
a.) PENTAGON b.) HETEROGENEOUS

Solution:
a.) The total number of letters of the word pentagon is 8. So, there is a total of 8! permutations in the word pentagon but there are 2 n's. Hence, the number of distinguishable permutation for the word pentagon is $P = \frac{8!}{2!} = 20,160$.

b.) There are 13 letters in the word heterogeneous but there are 4 e's and 2 o's. Hence, the number of distinguishable permutations is $P = \frac{13!}{4!2!} = 129,729,600$

Let us create problems and solve them.

Create two problems about solving the distinguishable permutations and show your solutions.

Questions to Ponder:

1. What did you consider in creating each problem?
2. How did you solve each problem?

Figure 1. Sample work example in the SSLM and the corresponding modified task

Conduct of the Pre-test. A pre-test was conducted for both experimental and control groups before the implementation of the intervention. The validated test was given to the two sections of Grade 10 students as the respondents.

Facilitation of Lessons for Control and Experimental Groups. Lessons on permutation and combinations and probability of simple events were given to both groups for 30 days (6 weeks).

Control Group. The control group learned permutations and combinations, and the probability of simple events through the tasks reflected in the module. These tasks may fall under any cognitive demand level.

For the control group, the following was done to facilitate the lessons.

The lesson was introduced through an introductory activity.

The teacher guided the students' discussion to reveal the purpose of the activity.

The concept was presented by telling them the definitions, rules, and formulas to be memorized.

The rules, procedures, and formulas were applied in the mathematics tasks listed in the SSLM. The learners were expected to perform the tasks.

The teacher provided activities from SSLM where the formula can be applied. The learners should apply mathematical concepts.

After that, the teacher provided drills and practice exercises from the SSLM for the students to learn the lessons.

Lastly, the teacher processed the learners' responses to the different activities to correct the misconceptions and enhance the learning outcomes.

Experimental Group. The experimental group was exposed to modified tasks for higher cognitive demand. These tasks were introduced for the students to learn the lessons. In learning the lessons, the teaching procedures in the control group were also followed. However, the following were additionally implemented.

The teacher presented modified tasks with higher cognitive demands as work examples and guided the learners on how to answer these tasks.

After the guided practice, the learners worked on modified tasks where they needed to find their own formulas and explain their plans to solve the problems. They also created different problems involving the concepts, devised their solutions, and provided their justifications or generalizations.

Conduct of the Post-test. Post-test was conducted for the control and experimental groups after the 30-day learning sessions. The same test items were given to both groups.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the activities found in the SSLM in terms of its cognitive demand level, the framework of Stein et al. (2000) was employed. The matrix below in Figure 2 shows a summary of the guide in analyzing the cognitive level of the mathematical tasks. The matrix below was used as a guide in the analysis of the tasks in Mathematics.

LOWER-LEVEL COGNITIVE DEMANDS	HIGHER-LEVEL COGNITIVE DEMANDS
<i>Memorization Tasks (Level 1)</i>	<i>Procedures with Connections Tasks (Level 3)</i>
Recalling previously acquired facts, rules, formulas, or definitions or memorizing such information.	Demand some degree of cognitive effort to connect conceptual ideas, usually characterized by multiple representations, and propose pathways that are broad and conceptually clear, rather than narrow and algorithmic.
<i>Procedures Without Connections Tasks (Level 2)</i>	<i>Doing Mathematics Tasks (Level 4)</i>
Follow algorithms and focus on finding the correct answers, where the utilization of a procedure is either explicitly stated or inferred from prior learning, experience, or task placement.	Demands a considerable degree of cognitive effort and non-algorithmic thought processes, lacks a predetermined or explicitly suggested approach from the task, instructions, or examples.

Figure 2. Stein et al. (2000) task analysis guide

Furthermore, the mathematics achievement of Grade 10 students across different cognitive demand levels was analyzed using mean scores. The normality of pre-test, post-test, and mean gain scores was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. To examine significant differences between pre-test scores, post-test scores, and mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups, independent sample t-tests were conducted. Additionally, dependent sample t-tests were used to determine significant differences between pre-test and post-test scores within both the experimental and control groups. In all tests, a 1% level of significance was used.

Results and Discussion

Cognitive Demand Level of the Mathematical Tasks in the Simplified Self-Learning Module (SSLM) for Mathematics in Grade 10

The tasks, with a total of 69 items from 8 different activities in the Simplified Self-Learning Module (SSLM), were analyzed by the researcher using the framework of Stein et al. (2000) to determine its cognitive demand levels. The results of the analysis were validated by two Master Teachers in Mathematics.

Table 1 shows that 47 out of the 69 items (68.11%) in the SSLM fell under Level 2, which emphasizes procedural knowledge without connections. This reliance on procedural tasks can lead to a surface-level understanding of mathematical concepts, which might not support long-term retention or the ability to transfer knowledge to different problems. It appears that students' time to practice mathematical concepts was primarily allotted to lower-demand tasks. In the 2022 PISA, a large percentage of Filipino students (84%) demonstrated competency up to Level 2 only.

Notably, there was no item in the SSLM classified as Level 4, which involves doing mathematics. This absence suggests a gap in the SSLM's ability to offer students opportunities to engage in more complex and integrative mathematical thinking. The lack of Level 4 tasks across all topics is particularly concerning, as almost none of the Filipino students attained the highest competencies in mathematics in the 2022 PISA.

Table 1. Level of cognitive demand of the mathematical tasks in the simplified self-learning module

SSLM Topics	No. of items	Cognitive Levels			
		Lower Cognitive Level		Higher Cognitive Level	
		Level 1 (Memorization)	Level 2 (Procedures without Connection)	Level 3 (Procedures with Connection)	Level 4 (Doing Mathematics)
Permutations	39	0	32	7	0
Combinations	20	0	15	5	0
Probability	10	0	0	10	0
Total	69	0	47	22	0
Percentage	100	0	68.11	31.88	0

Overall, the results indicate that more emphasis was placed on practice tasks that require low-level cognition, as evidenced by the greater number of items under Level 2. Each activity in the SSLM includes several items but generally focuses on one cognitive demand level only. This means that while the activities have multiple items, all the items engage students in the same cognitive task. There was no variation of cognitive demand within an activity. For instance, the activity in Figure 3 below has 20 items, all requiring computation, which limits the instructional time to lower-level cognitive tasks.

ACTIVITY 1: Compute each.				
1. $8!$	5. $6! 5!$	9. $\frac{10!}{2!+3!}$	13. ${}_5P_2 \cdot {}_3P_3$	17. ${}_{10}P_7 \div {}_8P_6$
2. $4! + 5!$	6. $\frac{6!(5!+3!)}{2!3!}$	10. $10! + 10!$	14. ${}_6P_2 + {}_6P_3$	18. ${}_{12}P_9 \div {}_{10}P_8$
3. $\frac{10!}{4!3!}$	7. $12!$	11. ${}_{10}P_{10}$	15. ${}_{11}P_8$	19. ${}_8P_6 \div {}_9P_4$
4. $\frac{(8!7!)}{2!3!}$	8. $8!(5!) + 2!(10!)$	12. ${}_{15}P_4$	16. ${}_9P_1 \div {}_8P_4$	20. ${}_1P_1$

Figure 3. Sample activity in permutations with level 2 – procedures without connections

The Pre-test Mean Scores of the Grade 10 Students in the Control and Experimental Group

Table 2 shows the comparative pre-test mean scores of students in the control and experimental groups prior to the experimental teaching. The pre-test had a total of 20 points divided equally into the four levels of cognitive demand. The control group had a total pre-test mean score of 6.43 (sd = 2.5) while the experimental group's mean score was 6.06 (sd = 2.15). The results show that the control group's mean scores were slightly higher than the experimental group in all cognitive levels. The total mean scores indicate about 30% performance in the pre-test by both groups. Based on the results, insights can be drawn that Mathematics teachers need to find teaching techniques that will help Grade 10 students improve their achievement in Mathematics and enhance learning outcomes in permutation, combination, and probability.

The Shapiro-Wilk test was employed to evaluate the normality of the pre-test scores for both the control and experimental groups due to the small sample size. The results show that the distribution of scores in both the control ($W = 0.96$, p -value = .31) and experimental ($W = 0.96$, p -value = .34) groups did not significantly deviate from the normal distribution.

The t-test results ($t = 0.62$, p -value = .53) in Table 2 indicate no statistically significant difference in the pre-test scores between the control and experimental groups. This suggests that both groups had comparable levels of mathematics achievement before the intervention, meaning they were comparable at the beginning of the study.

According to Prince et al. (2015), groups are considered comparable if they exhibit similar achievement levels before the start of the experiment. Additionally, it is important that both groups are heterogeneous, meaning that students with high scores are not clustered in one group, ensuring that the scores between groups are comparable.

Table 2. Comparative pre-test mean scores of the control and experimental group

Cognitive Demands	Total Points	Control $n = 30$		Experimental $n = 32$		t	df	p -value
		Mean	sd	Mean	sd			
Level 1	5	2.43	0.77	2.25	0.72	0.97ns	59	.33
Level 2	5	2.20	0.96	2.13	0.75	0.34ns	55	.73
Level 3	5	1.80	0.92	1.69	0.78	0.52ns	57	.61
Level 4	5	0	0	0	0	--	--	--
Total	20	6.43	2.5	6.06	2.15	0.62ns	57	.53

ns - not significant ($p < 0.01$)

The Post-test Mean Scores of the Grade 10 Students in the Control and Experimental Group

Table 3 shows the post-test mean scores of students in the control and experimental group after the experimental teaching. The control group scored a total post-test mean score of 12.97 or 64.8% (sd = 4.57) while the experimental group's mean score was 16.06 or 80.3% (sd = 2.44). All the cognitive level mean scores and consequently total mean scores reveal higher performance of the experimental

group. Interestingly, the difference in mean scores becomes bigger as the cognitive demand level increases in favor of the experimental group with lesser variability in scores. In cognitive Level 4, which demands intricate and non-algorithmic thought processes, the mean of 3.78 (75.6%) of the experimental group was 35.6% higher than the achievement of the control group.

The Shapiro-Wilk test was also used to assess the normality of the post-test scores and results show that both the control ($W = 0.96$, p -value = .29) and experimental groups ($W = 0.97$, p -value = .50) post-test scores are approximately normal.

The result of the t-test for all levels indicates no statistically significant difference in the post-test scores of the control and experimental groups for cognitive demand Level 1 ($t = 0.53$, p -value = .60) and Level 2 ($t = 1.28$, p -value = .20). This suggests that both groups have comparable achievement in lower cognitive demands after the experimental teaching. It may be noted that a heavier emphasis on lower cognitive tasks does not necessarily result in higher performance and conversely, a reduced emphasis on lower cognitive tasks did not necessarily result in lower performance in these tasks as in the case of the control and experimental group, respectively.

For higher cognitive demands, the experimental group performed significantly higher in Level 3 ($t = 2.05$, p -value < .05) and Level 4 ($t = 3.69$, p -value < .001). The results show that students in the experimental group, who were exposed to modified tasks requiring higher cognitive demands have developed a greater achievement for answering math questions that necessitate advanced cognitive processes.

Overall mean post-test score was statistically higher with the experimental group ($t = 3.29$, p -value < .001). The results manifest that students who are given exposure to higher cognitive demand levels are more successful in performing mathematical tasks. This conforms with the findings of Parrish and Bryd (2022) and Ruk (2021) indicating that placing value on higher cognitive demand for the learners will result in students achieving better in Mathematics.

Table 3. Comparative post-test mean scores of the control and experimental group

Cognitive Demands	Control <i>n</i> = 30		Experimental <i>n</i> = 32		Mean Difference	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> -value
	Mean	<i>sd</i>	Mean	<i>sd</i>				
	Level 1	4.26	1.23	4.41				
Level 2	3.67	1.18	4.06	1.24	0.39	1.28ns	60	.20
Level 3	3.03	1.56	3.81	1.42	0.78	2.05*	59	.04
Level 4	2.00	2.30	3.78	1.34	1.78	3.69**	46	<.001
Total	12.97	4.57	16.06	2.44	3.09	3.29**	44	<.001

** - significant at .01 level

Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Scores

Table 4 shows the data comparing the pre-test and post-test achievement of the control group. The pre-test mean score of 6.43 (32.1%) rose to 12.97 (64.8%) in the post-test, reflecting a mean difference of 6.54 (32.7%). This increase in mean scores can be attributed to the instruction received on the covered topics, which led to improved performance.

Additionally, the t-test results ($t = 7.88$, p -value < .001) indicate that the rise in total mean scores from the pre-test to the post-test is statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. These results suggest that students benefited from the instruction and self-learning modules, as evidenced by the increased post-test mean score.

The increase in each cognitive demand was also significant at .01 level. Among the cognitive demand levels, the mean showed a bigger increase in scores in level 1 and became lesser as the cognitive level increased.

Noticeably, none of the students in the control group answered the item with Level 4 cognitive demand during the pre-test but it is evident that some can do so in the post-test. This means that some student can just figure out their own how to accomplish higher cognitive tasks after the basic concepts are taken.

Table 4. Comparative pre-test and post-test mean scores of the control group

Cognitive Demands	Pre-Test		Post-Test		Mean Difference	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i> -value
	Mean	<i>sd</i>	Mean	<i>sd</i>			
Level 1	2.43	0.77	4.27	1.23	1.84	7.96**	<.001
Level 2	2.20	0.96	3.67	1.18	1.47	5.61**	<.001
Level 3	1.80	0.92	3.03	1.56	1.23	4.08**	<.001
Level 4	0	0	2.00	2.30	2.00	4.75**	<.001
Total	6.43	2.5	12.97	4.57	6.54	7.88**	<.001

** - significant at .01 level

Table 5 presents a comparison of the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group. The pre-test mean score of 6.06 (30.4%) rose to 16.06 (80.3%) in the post-test, representing an achievement increase of nearly 50%. The t-test results ($t = 16.60$, p -value < .001) demonstrate that the rise in mean scores from the pre-test to the post-test is statistically significant. Results indicate that students benefited from instruction together with the self-learning modules and the modified tasks for higher cognitive demand.

Table 5. Comparative pre-test and post-test mean scores of the experimental group

Cognitive Demands	Pre-Test		Post-Test		Mean Difference	t	p-value
	Mean	sd	Mean	sd			
Level 1	2.25	0.72	4.41	0.80	2.16	12.35**	<.001
Level 2	2.13	0.75	4.06	1.24	1.93	6.83**	<.001
Level 3	1.69	0.78	3.81	1.42	2.12	8.27**	<.001
Level 4	0	0	3.78	1.34	3.78	15.99**	<.001
Total	6.06	2.15	16.06	2.44	10	16.60**	<.001

** - significant at .01 level

Mean Gain Scores of the Control and Experimental Group

The Shapiro-Wilk test was also used to assess the normality of the mean gain scores and results show that both the control ($W = 0.98$, $p\text{-value} = .73$) and experimental groups ($W = 0.97$, $p\text{-value} = .42$) mean gain scores are approximately normal.

Table 6 shows the comparison of the mean gain scores between the experimental and control groups. The mean gain score for the experimental group was 3.47 points higher than that of the control group. The t-test results ($t = 3.38$, $p\text{-value} < .001$) reveal a significant difference in the mean gain scores between the two groups, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that the observed difference in mean gains is highly unlikely to be due to chance.

The results indicate that the experimental group experienced a greater increase in mathematics achievement compared to the control group. While both the use of SSLM and modified tasks for higher cognitive demands increased achievement as reflected in the mean gain scores, students exposed to higher cognitive demands showed greater improvement. This indicates that students performed better when exposed to tasks with higher cognitive demands.

When mathematics is taught and learned through tasks situated in real-world contexts, students are more inclined to perceive connections between the mathematics they are learning and various practical applications. Consequently, they are more likely to transfer the knowledge they acquire to similar and different contexts (Ibrahim & Rebello, 2012).

Table 6. Comparative mean gain scores of the control and experimental group

Cognitive Demands	Control n = 30		Experimental n = 32		Mean Difference	t	df	p-value
	Mean	sd	Mean	sd				
Level 1	1.83	1.26	2.16	0.99	0.33	1.11ns	55	.27
Level 2	1.47	1.43	1.94	1.61	0.47	1.22ns	60	.23
Level 3	1.23	1.65	2.13	1.45	0.90	2.25*	58	.03
Level 4	2.00	2.30	3.78	1.34	1.78	3.69**	46	<.001
Total	6.53	4.54	10.0	3.41	3.47	3.38**	54	<.001

** - significant at .01 level

Unlike the control group, the experimental group showed the greatest increase in mean score at the highest level of cognitive demand. This finding highlights the effectiveness of exposing the students to higher cognitive demand tasks where they practiced procedures with connections and presented solutions to the relevant math problems they had created. This approach requires students to engage in deeper thinking, problem-solving, and critical analysis, thereby enhancing their understanding and retention of the material. This positive outcome underscores the value of incorporating higher cognitive demand tasks in teaching Mathematics.

To highlight this finding, the pre-test and post-test scores on higher cognitive demand tasks by both control and experimental groups were cross-tabulated and shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Crosstabulation of pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents

Cognitive Demand	Pre-test Score	Post-test Score			
		Control		Experimental	
		0-2	3-5	0-2	3-5
Level 3	0-2	8	15	7	22
	3-5	1	6	0	3
Level 4	0-2	17	13	6	26
	3-5	0	0	0	0

In the control group, a notable number of respondents maintained their initial score range from the pre-test to the post-test, especially at higher cognitive demand levels. As shown in Table 7, at Level 3, only 15 (50%) of the control group students improved their scores from the 0-2 range to the 3-5 range. One student even regressed in performance. At Level 4, 78.33% of respondents who scored between 0-2 in the pre-test remained in the same range in the post-test, indicating minimal or no improvement at all. This trend is consistent across other levels, where a notable percentage of respondents remained stagnant suggesting that the current instruction using the SSLM was insufficient in significantly boosting cognitive performance.

In contrast, 22 (69%) of students in the experimental group increased in score range from 0-2 score range to 3-5 while all three in the highest score range sustained high performance. In Level 4, the experimental group exhibited more promising results. The improvement was more pronounced, with 81.25% of initially low scoring in this cognitive demand level advanced to the high 3-5 score range showing that the task modification was highly effective in enhancing cognitive demand at the highest level from the initial challenge.

Level IV: Doing Mathematics

After graduating from high school without sufficient funds to pursue college, Ana opted to work temporarily and save up for further education. She secured a job at Mr. Aquino's restaurant. However, she soon observed that there was no diversity in the restaurant's menu offerings. This observation prompted Mr. Aquino to seek her opinion on the matter. The absence of variety might be impacting the restaurant's business negatively. With a high probability of customer dissatisfaction and subsequent decline in revenue, she advised Mr. Aquino to consider introducing a wider range of dishes to attract a broader clientele and enhance the restaurant's profitability.

1. Formulate a problem involving the mathematical concepts in the above situation.
2. Solve the problem formulated.
3. Explain how this particular problem may help you in formulating conclusions and /or making decisions. In view of the fact that there will be several possible combinations, explain also why you should prepare certain dishes more often or less frequently.

Figure 4. Sample student output from the experimental group for level 4 task

Moreover, in the most cognitively demanding task (level 4), Figure 4 above displays the pre-test and post-test sample outputs of respondent. In the pre-test, there was no attempt, but in the post-test, the respondent successfully answered the problem. This highlights the effectiveness of the intervention, as evidenced by the respondent's ability to provide desired answers. These tasks entail formulating a problem based on given mathematical concepts, devising a solution, and drawing conclusions. The post-test output demonstrates the respondent's capacity to tackle tasks requiring higher cognition.

Conclusions

The results of the study revealed that most of the tasks in the SSLM for Mathematics Grade 10 were at lower cognitive demand levels, particularly procedures without connections, and there was no variation in the cognitive demands of the tasks within any given activity. Notably, none of the tasks reached the highest cognitive demand level of "doing mathematics." As a result, many students using the SSLM remained stagnant in performance, suggesting that the current instructional approach utilizing the SSLM is insufficient in significantly boosting cognitive performance. However, the study demonstrated that modifying mathematical tasks to increase cognitive demand was highly effective in enhancing achievement and improving students' performance on tasks requiring higher-order cognitive skills. Students who were taught using modified tasks performed better in mathematics, particularly on items demanding advanced cognitive processes.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that teachers should modify mathematical tasks in the SSLM to expose students to higher cognitive demands, thereby enhancing their achievement in Mathematics. Curriculum writers should incorporate tasks that engage students at all cognitive demand levels, ensuring a balanced distribution across levels 1 to 4. School officials should provide training for teachers on higher cognitive demand task modification and support their efforts to involve students in higher-order thinking activities. Additionally, further research should explore the cognitive demands of other modules, learning activities, and assessments in mathematics, focusing on maximizing student engagement and exposure to higher levels of thinking to improve educational outcomes.

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